

A VIBRATION TECHNIQUE TO OBTAIN FATIGUE

F. Just-Agosto, A. Peralta, B. Shafiq, D. Serrano
School of Engineering, University of Puerto Rico
Mayagüez, PR 00681, USA
fjust@me.uprm.edu

SUMMARY

A finite element based structural shape synthesis technique to design a vibration specimen for fatigue lifetime evaluation is developed. The procedure involves vibrating the specimen in resonance in order to produce a stress pattern in a given region that emulates a typical flexural fatigue test specifically those produced during three-point-bending (TPB). A design shape optimization procedure is described and validated for a foam core material with flexural fatigue experimental results.

Keywords: vibration, flexural fatigue, shape optimization, polyurethane foam, Three-point-bending

INTRODUCTION

Structures constructed with sandwich composites have the ability of tailoring the individual constituents yielding optimal designs with a high strength to weight ratio. This advantage over conventional materials has seen an increase in their use in many applications ranging from satellites, aircraft, automobiles, rail cars, wind energy systems, bridge construction, and marine vessels to name a few. In addition to the high strength to weight ratio, their resistance to corrosion has seen an increase in use in naval applications. Composite components are replacing steel yielding significant longer service lives with less maintenance costs. In naval vehicles with longer life spans, service loading encountered in events well below the elastic limits can accumulate into the millions of cycles (10^6 , 10^7), thus reinforcing the lifetime characterization of sandwich composites and their constituents very important.

Typical testing is usually performed on conventional servo-hydraulic machines that operate at low frequencies when compared to electrodynamic machines [1]. Today, fatigue testing is usually performed on hydraulic servo machines operating in the 1-10 Hz frequency range. In order to obtain one point in an S-N diagram for 10^6 cycles of testing, (at a frequency of 1Hz), a period of around 277 hrs is needed. If the sample endures 10^7 cycles around 115 days are required for the point. The typical suggested test procedure for an S-N-P diagram requires around 4 to 5 data points in the diagram [2] with each data point being determined with an average of 15 specimens tested at a given frequency and stress ratio. Consider a hypothetical case in which testing is charged at the rate of one dollar per hour. A typical test could cost between \$16,000 to \$20,000 dollars per material configuration (4 or 5 stress ratios with 15 samples per point at 10^6 cycles). Thus the ability to develop a test procedure that can operate at higher frequencies can reduce cost significantly. By increasing the testing rate by ten fold, significant saving occur reducing costs to a range of \$1,600 to \$2,000 per material configuration!

Fatigue lifetime characterization has been applied to a wide variety of engineering materials including sandwich composites and constituents such as foam cores as evidenced by the abundant literature [3-10] to name a few. Lifetime studies can address a wide array of issues that include, damage accumulation mechanisms, the effect of notches, environmental effects and the effects of frequency and stress level among others. However, most fatigue lifetime characterization is based on the low frequency testing of the specimens due mainly to the limitations imposed by the equipment [1, 2]. Furthermore, a high probability of disagreement is seen in the fatigue literature as the material system and testing conditions vary inconsistently from one laboratory to another [3, 4]. Thus in order to obtain meaningful statistical data, multiple repetitions are required [2]. It is easy to see that when a million cycles or more is required per specimen, testing may consume significant time and revenue at the normal operational frequencies of 1-2 Hz as used in conventional servo-hydraulic machines. Alternatives, such as, high frequency (up to 100hz) machines are available to expedite the fatigue testing time, however at a significant initial cost of purchase this may not be a practical alternative. In addition issues, such as, frequency (inertia) effects and temperature changes have been linked to high frequency testing [4, 10-13].

The paper aims to present an effective vibration technique that can be used to determine the fatigue life of a variety of engineering materials. Through shape optimization of the test specimen, a stress pattern mimicking the stress pattern obtained in flexural fatigue testing is obtained. The main idea behind the approach is that as long as the stress patterns match, the resulting lives obtained from fatigue and vibration testing must also correspond. This should be valid as long as frequency effects do not affect material properties significantly. The main differences between the current approach and work performed previously [14-16] is that for the first time the technique is actually verified against low frequency flexural fatigue tests and it is applied to foam core material found in sandwich composites as opposed to homogeneous metals. In addition, flexural vibration modes were used as opposed to torsional modes in references [14-16] with a vibration frequency at two orders of magnitude lower than that previously used [14, 16] and yet an order of magnitude higher than that normally used in TPB.

MATERIAL AND DESIGN METHODOLOGY

Material

The vibration specimen design methodology was performed using FR-7140 polyurethane foam manufactured by “General Plastic Manufacturing Company”. This foam was selected because its availability to be ordered directly from the manufacturer, consistency in the manufacturing and the accessibility of material property information specified through tests performed by the manufacturer.

T.P.B. Analysis

Before a design methodology can be developed, an accurate FEA model must be established. Static and fatigue TPB tests were performed for various initial rectangular specimens. These consisted of foam beams having dimensions of 16 cm length, 3.81 cm width and 1.9 cm thickness. Testing was performed using the ASTM C393 standard [17]. Fatigue TPB was modeled using solid elements with vertical restrictions at the

ends. Completely reversible ($R = -1, (\sigma_{\min.} / \sigma_{\max.})$) center beam loading with a frequency corresponding to 0.75 Hz, was used. The Von MISES stresses corresponding to the centerline were calculated and are shown in Figure 1

Figure 1: Stress Pattern IN TPB of FR-7140 foam Beam

Vibration Analysis

In order to ensure that FEA modeling predicts specimen behavior adequately, vibration testing is also performed. Six rectangular cantilever beam specimens were vibrated using a double cantilever beam configuration consisting of a double length beam with equivalent cantilever dimensions of 39 cm length, 4 cm width and 1.3 cm thickness. The frequency response function (FRF) containing the first three natural frequencies was determined by exciting the beam with random white noise. The FEA model used consisted of solid elements distributed along its length with a width corresponding to one eighth of the beams tested. By restricting the degrees of freedom at the cantilevered end appropriate boundary conditions were established. Performing computational modal analysis, values of 19.03, 109.45, and 321.40 Hz, were obtained. When compared to experimental results, these produced errors of 2.41, 2.77, and 8.84 percent respectively. Table 1, shows the values and errors generated during this step of

Table 1: First three Natural Frequencies from experiments and FEM

Natural Frequency	Experimental (FRF)	FEM (ANSYS)	Percent Error
1st	19.5 Hz	19.03 Hz	2.41%
2nd	106.6 Hz	109.45 Hz	2.77%
3 rd	295.3 Hz	321.40 Hz	8.84%

establishing the FEA model. After an adequate model was obtained, a harmonic analysis for each of the beam's first three transverse natural frequencies using the same forcing

amplitude has in testing was performed. Here the Von Misses centerline stress pattern for a completely reversible loading was determined. The results of the Three mode shapes are shown in Figure 2. It is clearly evident that the stress pattern generated at the first resonance is significantly greater than those corresponding to the second and third resonances. Based on this observation the first mode shape was selected as the starting point in the geometric specimen optimization procedure described next.

Figure 2: Von Misses centerline stress profile for the first natural frequencies.

Geometric Optimization

By examining Figure 2 it is evident that the highest stress occurs at the cantilever end during the first mode of vibration. In order to mimic three-point-bending in a given region, the stress profile must significantly change. This can be readily accomplished in two forms; the first is obtained by changing the loading pattern in other words, the boundary conditions and the second the geometry of the specimen, which is the approach used here. As a first step in this procedure, a parametric model of a cantilever beam with variable dimensioning is established. The model used is shown in Figure 3 here, H1, H2, H3 and H4 correspond to thickness values that can be varied and are located at distances of zero, L1, L2 and L3 from the cantilevered end. The width of the beam is designated by W. Initial constraints based upon the shaker capabilities and available equipment set the maximum dimension of L3 to be 39 cm with a restriction of a first resonance less than 40 Hz.

Figure 2: Parametric model used in geometric optimization.

The basic procedure consists of varying the H_1 , H_2 , H_3 , and H_4 dimensions of an initial rectangular specimen of uniform height of 1.27 cm. In order to reduce the stress at the cantilevered end, the thickness at location H_1 is increased in ten percent increments of its initial value. After each change modal analysis is performed to determine the new stress pattern and ensure that the first resonance does not exceed the given constraint. This procedure is usually repeated several times until a decrease of twenty percent of the initial stress is obtained as seen by comparing Figures 4a and 4b. By decreasing the values of H_2 and H_3 , the maximum stress occurring on the beam changes its location from the cantilever end. Again modal analysis is performed and values are examined to ensure that the changes are yielding desired output. It should be noted that during the process the values of H_2 and H_3 may be individually or simultaneously changed until the desired stress pattern is obtained. This process was repeated several times until the pattern shown in Figure 4c was obtained. Increasing the value of H_4 further changes the stress pattern to resemble that found in TPB. Once again the interactive procedure of calculating the stress pattern and ensuring the first resonance is within the limits was repeated. After several variations, the resulting pattern shown in Figure 4d was established. As seen in the figure the peak value generated a stress ratio of around 0.6 the ultimate stress found by TPB.

Varying the values of L_1 and L_2 can also alter the location and shape of the Von Mises stress curve. Here values of L_1 and L_2 were increased and decreased respectively to produce the Von Mises centerline curve shown in Figure 4e. An image of the final test specimen along with the mesh distribution used in the calculations is shown in Figure 5. A comparison of the Von Mises vibration centerline profile along with that obtained by TPB is shown in Figure 6. The process of alternating the values of H_2 , H_3 , H_4 , L_1 and L_2 can be continued to produce a better distribution similarity. However, the most critical region should be where the test specimen is designed to fatigue as seen as the region with the highest stress ratio in Figure 6.

Figure 4: Geometric Optimization Process: a) initial model, b) increasing H1, c) decreasing H2 and H3, d) increasing H4, e) modifying L1 and L2

Figure 5: Optimized vibration FR-7140 test specimen with meshing used for analysis

Figure 6: Comparison of the predicted Von Mises centerline stress profile from TPB specimens and vibration test specimens.

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

In order to validate the specimen design methodology, experimental verification was performed. A servo-hydraulic machine was used for static and fatigue testing. Static testing was accomplished using the ASTM C-393 standard. An average ultimate stress value of 25.2 MPa with a standard deviation of 0.62MPa was obtained. In addition fully reversible, ($R=-1, \sigma_{\min.} / \sigma_{\max.}$), TPB fatigue testing at room temperature was done on FR7140 foam specimens using a 0.75 Hz sinusoidal loading frequency. In order to generate the FR-7140 foam beam fatigue curve, a total of sixteen specimens were tested. Four specimens were evaluated for each stress ratio of σ/σ_{ult} , corresponding to 0.55, 0.49, 0.43, and 0.39. The total numbers cycles before catastrophic failure were recorded and data required to generate an S-N curve was taken. Vibration testing was done at room temperature using an electromagnetic shaker. Data analysis and excitation signal generation was performed using a 6-channel DSPT SigLab Dynamic Signal Analysis (DSA) system. A Laser Doppler Vibrometer (LDV) was used to measure the beams transverse motion. As with TPB testing 16 specimens were vibrated (four specimens for each stress ratio). The values of stress ratios (0.55, 0.49, 0.43, and 0.39) were the same as those used in TPB. Specimens were vibrated in resonance at 19.25 Hz and the time required to failure was recorded. As with TPB fatigue analysis all failures were catastrophic in nature. The data required to generate S-N curves was also taken. Figure 7 show the TPB fatigue tests set up and a designed specimen undergoing the fatigue vibration test.

Figure 7: Photos of TPB and vibration testing being performed on FR-7140 specimens.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The S-N diagrams of the FR-7140 foam under TPB and vibration fatigue testing exhibited an exponential behavior with similar scatter observed at the different stress ratios. Initial results showed that vibration fatigue data always predicted a higher fatigue life than those from TPB. One possible explanation for this behavior could be attributed to the effect of contact stress encountered in the jig used to hold the TPB specimens (see Figure 7). When values are calculated in typical TPB tests, the effect of the contact stress produced by the holding pins is not determined. Thus when comparing TPB stress ratios with vibration values a longer fatigue life is predicted. By estimating the contact stress has a pin on a flat surface [18] and considering this in the calculation of the Von-Misses stress, the vibration results could be adjusted. As a result of this consideration the errors between both techniques were reduced considerably. Figure 8 shows the corrected vibration S-N curve compared with that of the TPB curve within its corresponding ninety percent confidence bounds.

Figure 8: Fatigue curves for FR-7140 foam considering contact stress adjustment

By examining Figure 8, it is clearly evident that the developed methodology can be used as a feasible alternative to TPB testing when applicable. The vibration technique developed performed 26 times faster than the TPB test performed yielding similar results. Thus the proposed objective to develop and prove an alternative method using a vibration technique to simulate TPB fatigue testing was successful.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the support and guidance of Dr. Yapa Rajapakse, the ONR program Manager. The research was conducted under ONR grant #N000140611043.

References

1. Harris C.M., "Shock and Vibration Handbook", 4th edition, 1995, *McGraw-Hill*, United States, 25-14.
2. Collins J. A., "Failure of Materials in Mechanical Design, 2nd edition, 1993, John Wiley & Sons, United States, 194-228.
3. D. Zenkert, A. Shipsha, M. Burman, Fatigue of closed cell foams, vol. 8, p. 517-538, 2006.
4. Sharma, S., Gibson, R. and Ayorinde, E. (2006). Fatigue of Foam and Honeycomb Core Composite Sandwich Structures: A Tutorial, *Journal of Sandwich Structures and Materials*, 8:263-319.
5. Stone, H., Fatigue Testing of Flexible Foams, *Journal of Cellular Plastics*, p.47-60, 1983.
6. D. Roosen, Fatigue behavior of sandwich foam core materials: Comparison of different core materials, *Journal of Advanced Materials*, vol. 37, no. 1, p.38-42.
7. S. Yau and G. Mayer, Fatigue crack propagation in polycarbonate foam, *Materials science and Engineering*, vol. 78, p. 111-114, 1986.
8. F. Noble and J. Lilley, Fatigue crack growth in polyurethane foam, *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 16, p. 1801-1808, 1981.
9. Mahi A, Farooq M and Sahraoui D. Mechanical behavior of Sandwich Composite Material under Cyclic Fatigue, *New Trends in Fracture and Fatigue-Metz*, 2002:April, France.
10. Kulkarni N, Mahfuz H, Jeelani S and Carlsson L. Fatigue Crack Growth and Life Prediction of Foam Core Sandwich Composite under Flexural Loading, *Composite Structures* 2003:59: 499-505.
11. Kanny, K., Mahfuz, H., Thomas, T. and Jeelani, S.(2004).Temperature Effects on the Fatigue Behavior of Foam Core Sandwich Structures, *Polymers and Polymer Composites*.
12. K. Kanny, H. Mahfuz, Flexural fatigue characteristics of sandwich structures at different loading frequencies, *Composite Structures*, Vol. 67, No. 4, p. 403-410, 2005.
13. V. Barron, M. Buggy, N. McKenna, Frequency effects on the behavior of Carbon fiber reinforced polymer laminates, *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 36, No. 7, p. 1755-1761, 2001.
14. O. Scott, H. Shen, T. George, C. Cross, J. Calcaterra, Development of an improved high cycle fatigue criterion, *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, Vol. 129, No. 1, p. 162-169, 2007.
15. T. George, J. Seidt, M. Shen, T. Nicholas, C. Cross, (2003) "Development of a novel Vibration-Based fatigue testing methodology", *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol. 26, p. 477-486, 2004.
16. T. George, M. Shen, O. Scott, T. Nicholas, C. Cross, J. Calcaterra, Goodman diagram via vibration based fatigue testing, *Transactions of the ASME*, Vol. 127, p. 58-64, 2005.
17. ASTM Standard, C393-62. "Standard Test Methods for the Flexural Properties of Flat Sandwich Constructions", *Annual book of the ASTM Standards*, American Society of Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, PA, USA
18. J. Shigley, C. Mischke, "Mechanical Engineering Design", fifth edition, 1989, *McGraw-Hill, Inc*, United States, 71-75.